

1 **Genomic instability, exhaustion, transcriptional noise, and clearance of genomically unstable cells.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We illustrate here the concept that a measure of transcriptional noise will reflect the level of genomic
8 instability and vice versa, and that genomic instability as observed in BRCA mutant cells is intrinsically
9 linked to exhaustion (e.g. Tox family expression), and so the intrinsic link between genomic instability and
10 exhaustion executes an immunologic function related to transcriptional noise and homeostatic control of
11 gene expression: a cell extrinsic senescent-type clearance of genomically unstable cells.

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